

TEACHER'S ROLE IN THE PROCESS OF MOTIVATING LEARNERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7935486>

Annotation: This article focus on studying widely spread definitions of motivation in language learning and teaching. It also tried to find theoretical considerations about motivating students to be effective learners and factors increasing their motivation. This article aimed to find the most important factors that influence the motivation of the students to learn the English language and to uncover the character and intensity of these factors. Moreover, the research analysed the motivational factors in relation to the gender, year of study and the grades in English to reveal the differences between the motivations of the investigated groups of students.

Key words: layer of motivation, connecting principles, self-access quizzes, learner's passion; A number of initiatives in Second Language Assessment (SLA) research over the past decade have helped clarify our understanding of motivation and the specific psychological and behavioral components of motivation that we as teachers can influence. We can identify three levels or layers of motivation in language learning that are "operational," or accessible to direct influence by the teacher. To the extent that a teacher can tap into any or all of these layers, he or she is more likely to become a "motivating" teacher.

The first layer of motivation: Finding your passion – The first layer or the central core of motivation is what might be called finding your passion." It would be argued that all successful learning – not only language learning – is somehow connected to a learner's passion. Passion, in this sense, means a person's central goals in life, the things the learner cares about most, and the things that move him or her emotionally. It is not meant that a learner needs to become passionate about learning English in order to succeed. Rather, the learner needs to find a way to connect English learning to his or her real passion in life. [1]

The teacher can help learners to bring their passion into the classroom in several ways. One is by introducing "hot elements" in the classroom — music, movies, fads, current topics, personalities, games, and so on — in order to trigger learners' real interests. The teacher can then use these triggers to build a class culture. If we introduce, or if we allow the learners themselves to bring in, samples of current songs, clippings of famous people, or photos or video clips, we invite greater engagement in the classroom.

Another way of helping learners find their passion is by organizing class activities around the theme of self-expression. There are a number of approaches here: personalized tasks, idea journals, speaking circles, interactive questionnaires. When learners realize that the content of the class is their personal lives, and that the teacher responds to them as people, not just as language learners, we invite a deeper level of commitment and motivation.

A third way of generating passion is through the psychological principle of "immediacy" – using "yourself" as a model of enthusiasm and motivation for learning!

The second layer of motivation: Changing your reality – In virtually every language learning setting, but particularly in EFL settings, learners cannot make and sustain sufficient progress in the L2 because they do not receive enough instruction, not nearly enough attention in class, not nearly enough input or meaningful interaction or opportunities for serious output. Some studies in language immersion have estimated that a typical learner needs a minimum

of four hours a week of quality contact with a language in order to make progress. Even if this estimate is not true for all learners, it is clear to most EFL teachers that learners need more language instruction than we can provide in our classrooms. Learners need more quality instruction - input, interaction, and opportunities for meaningful output – not only to make progress, but in order to maintain a sufficiently strong connection to the language and to build their own motivation for learning.

In my own language teaching and in my materials development, I now consider it a major part of my job to help students find opportunities for engaging learning tasks outside the classroom. Helping learners find quality “homework” is essential to maintain quality learning in the classroom. The ideas are endless: direct students to quality language learning websites (or build your own, as many teachers have done), make available quality audio, video, and multimedia learning sources, develop a small library of accessible readers and supplementary materials and self-access quizzes, worksheets and games. Spending classroom time to help students select, share, and evaluate their out-of-class work with English is just as important as covering a lesson in the textbook.

Helping students “change their reality” means moving them toward seeing language learning in a different way. It means helping them take simple, self-directed steps to make choices about learning. The first step is the most important, because it’s the one that can ignite this layer of motivation.

The third layer of motivation: Connecting to learning activities - Connecting refers to the engagement of intention, attention, and memory in the activity itself. All teachers want their students to connect with the learning activities we prepare, yet we often fail to take concrete steps that will lead to better connection. Here are a few “connecting principles” that I try to employ in my own teaching materials, such as: World View:

- Use personalized warm ups to lead into an activity. This creates relevance an essential condition for memory to work effectively. Aim to get all students involved in the warm up.
- Make each learning activity as vivid and tangible as possible. Use provocative topics. Include visual aids (pictures, charts) and tangible references (games, boards, index cards) to engage students’ attention. Provide variety in your learning activities so that students can try out different learning styles (interpersonal, kinesthetic, musical, etc.).
- Make sure that each learner is involved, and everyone has an intention in every activity. Assign roles in pair and group activities. Monitor as closely as you can to be sure that each student, especially the shy and weaker ones, remains active. It’s important to have everyone on board.
- Include inductive learning in your lesson. Be sure that students have an opportunity to discover things on their own – grammar points, pragmatic patterns, and new vocabulary.
- Give students a chance to reflect. It’s always easier to teach deductively through direct presentations, but discovery learning is more meaningful and more permanent.
- Provide feedback on all levels of language progress. Progress in language involves more than just gradual mastery of grammar and vocabulary. Give feedback on elements of performance that affect students’ motivation: their success in an activity and their level of engagement.

When the learning of a second language takes place at home with the support of the neighborhood and local schools, it seems to be learned with relative ease, sometimes automatically. But when the process happens in the classroom, the school social context and the special conditions under which such learning takes place have a decisive influence. The domain of the motivation to learn the language is very broad and includes many complex areas. Indeed, all the categories which were investigated in this thesis would be worth further research, especially, the teachers' influence as it comprises the highest potential for affecting the motivation of the students to learn the English language.

In conclusion, I would like to state that investigating the motivation to learn in this thesis greatly contributed to my professional growth as a teacher and it made me realise the importance of the role of the teacher in the learning process of my students. Therefore, I hope that this study will also help to other teachers to understand their enormous capacity to affect their students' willingness to learn the English language.

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